

Citation

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Technology transfer: The role of culture in transferring technology

Abstract

The paper presents the results of an empirical investigation into the relationships among cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing technology. The framework of the study was developed to address these two dimensions of the study. For the cultural aspects, cultural dimensions of power distance, individualism-collectivism, masculinity-femininity, and uncertainty avoidance were used. For the technology transfer, the embodiment forms of technology approach were used. The embodiment forms perspective views technology as comprising four components, namely, object-embodied form, human-embodied form, document-embodied form, and institution-embodied form. The study was conducted in a major local/foreign joint venture apparel manufacturing company that was involved in transferring manufacturing technology to Sri Lanka. The data was collected through a questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the regression method. The results of the investigation revealed high transfer of the components of manufacturing technology. However, the investigation did not reveal any significant linear relationship between any of the cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing technology components. Therefore, though literature emphasises that cultural factors could affect cross-cultural project work, it is not evident in our investigation.

Keywords: Apparel manufacturing industry, Embodiment forms of technology, Hofstede's cultural dimensions, Technology transfer.

Introduction

The role of technology in achieving competitiveness, growth, and development has become a matter of global interest. Ayres (1988) refers to technology as "the wealth of nations". It may be said that for good or evil, economic growth draws its vital nourishment from technology, without which, no matter how favourable all other factors might have been, modern development would have been essentially inconceivable (Ramanathan, 1990). The need to acquire and use the technology has become a matter of urgency for the countries that are less advanced in technological capabilities. In this context, the ever-increasing application of technology has led to considerable sophistication of economic activities, which in turn caused a great upliftment of the standards of living in the developed countries (Sharif 1988). Now, even the developing countries have recognised the role of technology as a strategic variable for economic development (Sharif 1988). At the micro level, the impact of technology on business enterprises has been well documented (Malmgren, 1988; Nelson, 1977; Ramanathan, 1990). Manufacturing technology is a priced asset that creates value through the production of goods and services. Porter (1985) states that technological change is one of the principal drivers of competition as it plays a major role in industry structural change, as well as in creating new industries.

One of the ways of acquiring technology is through technology transfer, especially through international joint venture arrangements (Ramanathan, 1994). However, national differences

may affect technology acquisition and usage, implementation, structure, and characteristics, given that many international and multinational companies need to transfer or develop technologies in a number of different countries (Abdul-Gader, 1997; Martinson, 1991). In this regard, a number of factors have been suggested to cause national differences, including a country's political, economic, and physical environment, and cultural dynamics (Ford et al, 2003). However, a commonly stated impact of the globalization of business is the need for managers and researchers to improve their understanding of the role of national culture (Bing, 2004; Lenartowicz and Roth, 1999; Newman and Nollen, 1996). In this context, Hofstede (1996) states that at one time there was a discussion about whether organizations and organizing are bound by national cultures. Some people adhered to the "culture-free" hypotheses, but that concept has died in East Asia. Even though organizations have universal characteristics, no one can deviate from culture; organizations are to some extent culture-bound. This is also true in the field of technology transfer, as there have been several calls for research that integrates the transfer of technology and national culture (Hill et al, 1998; Zelkowitz et al, 1998).

Hofstede's work appears to be flourishing in disciplines such as organizational behaviour, marketing, psychology, and sociology. Only a few studies have been found on information technology transfer, when "international" or "national culture" issues are discussed (Hill et al, 1998). However, none of these studies have been found in relation to manufacturing technology transfer. Therefore, it is important to discern in what ways cultural dimensions influence in transferring manufacturing technology. Further, it is also evident from our preliminary investigations that technology transfer research has not extensively integrated cultural dimensions into the development of hypotheses, models, or theories.

In the Sri Lankan context, most tend to believe that the Sri Lankan apparel manufacturing industry is a labour-intensive and less technology-intensive industry. Though the apparel manufacturing industry was introduced to Sri Lanka as a solution for its unemployment problem, later on, the industry identified the need to acquire high-tech machinery and production techniques to be competitive in the global market. Most of the Sri Lankan apparel manufacturing companies use technology transfer mechanisms through local/foreign joint venture arrangements to acquire foreign technology. To facilitate technology transfer, cross-cultural teams have been formed. However, our preliminary investigations into technology transfer projects revealed that not all such projects had achieved expected outcomes. Some of the projects had taken longer time periods than expected to complete the transfer process, while some had not been successful in continuing manufacturing operations based on the newly acquired technologies through the transfer process.

Objectives of the research

In this research, we take the stand that technology transfer in local/foreign joint ventures can be adversely affected by the cultural understanding between partners. Thus, without better cultural understanding, it is unrealistic to have expectations on the extent of technology that can be transferred through local/foreign joint venture arrangements. Therefore, the main objective of the research is to investigate the role of culture in transferring manufacturing technology. In doing so, we first investigate the level of manufacturing technology transferred based on the embodiment forms perspective of process technology (Asian and Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology, 1989; Sharif, 1988; Technology Atlas Team, 1987). Second, we investigate cultural dimensions based on dimensions introduced by Hofstede (1980, 1983).

Third, we investigated whether there is a relationship between cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing technology.

The rest of this paper is presented in four parts. The first examines in some detail the theoretical background on different perspectives of technology, technology transfer, and Hofstede's cultural dimensions, to build up the framework for the study. This is followed by research methodology detailing population and sample, method of data collection, and methods of data analysis. The results of the analysis are presented next. The paper concludes the discussion by presenting implications of the results and identifying areas of future research.

Theoretical background and framework of the study

Different perspectives on technology

For effective transfer of technology, technology should not be treated as a “black box” (Ramanathan, 1994, p. 221). In opening the “black box”, different researchers have viewed technology from different perspectives. The four main perspectives that have governed the definition of technology are technology as a transformer perspective, technology as a tool perspective, technology as a knowledge perspective, and technology as an embodiment forms perspective (Ramanathan, 1994).

Technology as a transformer perspective stresses the importance of organising activities in order to achieve desired transformations, thereby bringing into focus the importance of managerial issues (Ramanathan, 1994). One of the popular definitions of this perspective is “technology is a set of principles and techniques useful to bring about change towards desired ends” (Taylor, 1971, as in Ramanathan, 1994, p. 224). A tool perspective emphasises the importance of machines and human-machine interactions. A popular definition of this perspective is “any product or process, any physical equipment or method of doing or making by which human capability is extended” (Schon, 1967, as in Ramanathan, 1994, p. 225). Technology as a knowledge perspective highlights the importance of know-how and know-why and implicitly introduces the role of human skills in gathering, using, and updating knowledge. One of the popular definitions of this perspective is “technology is scientific, engineering, and managerial knowledge which makes possible the conception, design, development, production, and distribution of goods and services (Gibson, 1976, as in Ramanathan, 1994, p. 226). The technology as embodiment forms perspective views technology as comprising of two major parts: a tangible and palpable part which is referred to by terms such as 'hardware' - material technology, capital goods, apparatus, tools, and equipment; and an intangible knowledge component which is described by terms such as "software", "brain ware", "social technology"- theories, technical and commercial information, definitional systems, practical knowledge, know-how, skills, and systems and structures of control, coordination, motivation, and rewards systems (Ramanathan, 1994). Thus, it could be said that the technology as embodiment forms perspective is the eclectic approach based on the ideas generated by the other three perspectives (Ramanathan, 1994). A popular definition of this perspective is “technology has three separate dimensions: 'apparatus,' referring to the physical equipment itself; 'technique,' referring to the skills and knowledge required to use the equipment, and 'organization,' referring to systems and structures of control and coordination (Winner, 1977, as in Ramanathan, 1994, p. 227).

Based on the embodiment forms perspective, polytrophic components of technology for a desired manufacturing system can be discerned into four different elementary forms (Asian and

Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology, 1989; Sharif, 1988; Technology Atlas Team, 1987). These are,

- Object-embodied forms of technology or "Technoware", which can be materials, the production tools, and the end product type;
- Human-embodied forms or "Humanware" which essentially represent the know-why type and include knowledge, skills, and experience of individual human beings or groups;
- Record-embodied forms or "Inforware" relating to that part of software which includes the know-how type, such as processes, techniques, methods, pertinent facts, and relationships such as those described in publications, documents, and blueprints;
- Institution-embodied forms or "Orgaware" which activate the interaction of the system with the physical and social environment

(Asian and Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology, 1989; Sharif, 1988; Technology Atlas Team, 1987).

An in-depth explanation of the nature and structure of the four components of technology, in the context of manufacturing process technology, is provided in Ramanathan (1994).

Technology transfer

The term technology transfer, which is also referred to as technology flows or diffusion of technology, implies the movement of technology from the technology owning entity (the transferor) to the receiving entity (transferee). If the transfer is successful, it implies the proper understanding and effective use of the technology by the receiving entity (Ramanathan, 1994). In general, there are two major classes of technology transfer, namely, vertical technology transfer and horizontal technology transfer.

Vertical technology transfer represents a flow from laboratory research through developmental stages and ultimately to commercialization. If a firm develops its own technology, which it then commercializes, then vertical technology transfer is said to have occurred (Ramanathan, 1994). Horizontal technology transfer is essentially the transfer of established technology from one operational environment to another. The environments can be international as well as intranational. If a firm acquires a technology from outside and uses it in that form, then pure horizontal transfer is said to have taken place (Ramanathan, 1994). In some situations, technology acquired elsewhere is adapted and perhaps improved before use. In such a case, both horizontal and vertical transfers have taken place (Ramanathan, 1994). The focus of this research is on horizontal manufacturing technology transfer.

Embodiment forms a perspective of technology in manufacturing technology transfer.

The transfer is successful only if it leads to the eventual acquisition and balanced development of all four components of technology. Thus, when transferring technology, it should examine the extent to which the four components are likely to be transferred (Ramanathan, 1994). For instance, when a firm purchases plant and equipment, the main component transferred is technology. The hardware is not developed unless the transferor agrees to provide training to the contractor and support hardware. Of course, it is possible that the transferee already has the necessary hardware (Ramanathan, 1994). The transferee should also ensure that at least the *tai*, *toi*, *tmi*, and *hfi* elements of inforware are obtained. Normally, *tdi*, *tpi*, *hbi*, the *OSI* elements of inforware, and orgaware are never transferred during the purchase of plant and equipment. Thus, when a firm purchases plant and equipment, it should simultaneously embark upon programmes to develop the "missing" components so that technology transfer will be effective

(Ramanathan, 1994). Firms that develop these missing components successfully will be more effective than those that do not, even though both may have similar technology. This is a clear message that emerges from Jaikumar's (1986) study of U.S. and Japanese flexible manufacturing systems. Local/foreign joint ventures have the potential of proving to be good mechanisms for comprehensive technology transfer through close interaction between the transferor and transferee, as there is a considerable scope for acquiring technoware, upgrading humanware, acquiring critical elements of inforware, and even emulating the transferor orgaware (Ramanathan, 1994).

Hofstede's dimensions of culture

While available methodologies and operationalizations of national culture are valuable and add to the understanding of national culture and its influence on organizations, Hofstede's proposed dimensions of national culture are very commonly used (Ford et al, 2003). These dimensions allow national-level analysis and are standardized to allow multiple country comparisons. In proposing cultural dimensions, Hofstede (1980) argued that the "survival of mankind will depend to a large extent on the ability of people who think differently to act together" (1980, p. 9). The argument was that to be able to act together, people must understand and be aware of the differences between cultures. Culture was defined as "the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one human group from another" (Hofstede 1980, p. 25). This collective programming is based on values: "... a broad tendency to prefer certain states of affairs over others" (Hofstede 1980, p. 19 and 25). In other words, members of the same culture will be similar in the way that they would prefer to view the world (Ford et al, 2003). Researchers from a number of fields are familiar with the work of Hofstede and the four dimensions of national culture that he defined originally (a fifth was added later). Originally identified, the four dimensions are individualism-collectivism, power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and masculinity-femininity. These dimensions are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Hofstede's cultural dimensions

Dimension	Description
Individualism-collectivism	This represents a continuum. An individualist culture is one in which the ties between individuals are loose. On the other hand, a collectivist culture finds people integrated into strong, cohesive groups. Cultures high in individualism will value personal time and personal accomplishments. Whereas cultures high in collectivism will value the group's well-being more than individual desires, the belief is that it is best for the individual if the group is cohesive.
Power distance	The extent to which the less powerful members of institutions within a country expect and accept that power is distributed unequally. Cultures that are high in power distance are illustrated by decisions being made by superiors without consultation with subordinates and employees being fearful of disagreeing with their superiors; whereas cultures that are low in power distance will have a more participative and egalitarian relationship between superiors and subordinates.
Uncertainty avoidance	The extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by uncertain or unknown situations is measured from weak to strong. Uncertainty avoidance is "related to anxiety, need for security and dependence upon experts" (Hofstede 1980, p. 10). A culture that is high in uncertainty avoidance would exhibit a rule orientation, prefer employment stability, and exhibit stress as the members of the culture try to explain, mitigate, and minimize the uncertainty that is inherent to life.
Masculinity-femininity	Initially, this dimension had been defined in terms of social gender roles and the distinctions made. When this is applied to the national culture as a whole, the gender roles view (social roles for the different sexes) is the appropriate interpretation. However, when this dimension is applied to the workplace, "Masculine countries stressed pay, security and job content; feminine countries stressed relationships and physical conditions" (Hofstede 2001, p. 313).

In addition to these four dimensions, Hofstede and Bond (1988) subsequently defined a fifth dimension, long-term orientation or "Confucian dynamism". As we see, Hofstede's original work defined four dimensions of national culture, but a fifth was added several years later. Further, almost all references to Hofstede's work cite the original 1980 publication where the four dimensions were initially defined (Ford et al, 2003). Therefore, in order to provide a reasonable and consistent scope to this research, we followed the 1980 publication and its subsequent editions.

One of the main advantages of Hofstede's framework is that it allows the comparison of studies across methodologies and contexts. Several studies applied these dimensions to describe groups or individuals (Iqbaria et al, 1995; Straub, 1994). Hofstede's dimensions were also used in analyzing technological issues in information technology transfer (Hill et al, 1998). Further, in the Sri Lankan context, these dimensions were used to analyze their influence on teamwork (De Silva, 2003). However, no studies have been found that used Hofstede's dimensions to describe manufacturing technology transfer in local/foreign joint ventures.

Hypotheses

Four hypotheses have been developed to facilitate the third objective of the study, i.e., to identify the relationship between the transfer of manufacturing process technology and cultural dimensions. The hypotheses are as follows.

- H₁: The greater the power distance of the personnel involved, the better the technology transfer would be.
- H₂: The greater the collectivism of the personnel involved, the better the technology transfer would be.
- H₃: The greater the masculinity of the personnel involved, the better the technology transfer would be.
- H₄: The greater the uncertainty avoidance of the personnel involved, the better the technology transfer would be.

Research Methodology

Design of the study

Qualitative studies are rich and lead to an in-depth understanding. But they are expensive and time-intensive and do not readily lend themselves to comparisons. Surveys, on the other hand, tend to follow the positivist paradigm and use quantitative methodology. One of the main advantages we see in Hofstede's culture framework and embodiment forms perspective of manufacturing technology is that these allow comparison of studies across methodologies and contexts. Therefore, we decided to utilize the survey method.

A company-based survey was conducted to achieve the research objectives. A local/foreign joint venture company was selected from the Sri Lankan apparel manufacturing industry. This company uses cutting-edge technology in garment and fabric knitting and has been involved in numerous technology transfer projects and technology upgrading projects to be competitive in the industry. For the research, a manufacturing technology transfer project of this company was taken into consideration, which started in the 2000, August and continued for a period of two years. Foreign specialists from the UK, Germany, and Italy worked in the transfer project along with local staff members of the company. During the two years, local staff members were also

given training opportunities to go abroad to broaden their understanding of technical as well as cultural aspects.

Population and sample of the study

It was decided to take responses from all 32 local staff members who were involved in the manufacturing technology transfer project during the above-mentioned timeframe of the selected company. Unfortunately, the foreigners who were involved in the project had already left the country after completing their roles. The characteristics of all the local staff members who are involved in the manufacturing technology transfer project are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the respondents (in percentages)

<u>Age</u>		<u>Years of service(in total)</u>	
26 to 30 years	9.4	Less than 6 years	46.9
31 to 35 years	46.9	6 to 10 years	18.7
36 to 40 years	21.8	11 to 15 years	9.4
41 to 45 years	15.6	16 to 20 years	6.3
More than 46 years	6.3	21 to 25 years	18.7
<u>Gender- Male</u>		<u>Years of service in the present company</u>	
	100	Less than one year	3.1
<u>Civil status</u>		1 to 2 years	3.1
Single	12.5	3 to 4 years	81.2
Married	87.5	5 to 7 years	6.3
<u>Religion</u>		More than 7 years	6.3
Buddhist	71.9	<u>Level in the management</u>	
Christian	28.1	Lower management	40.6
<u>Highest educational qualification</u>		Middle management	40.6
Postgraduate degree	28.1	Senior management	12.5
Degree or equivalent	50.0	Management advisor	6.3
Diploma	03.1	<u>Department in which they work</u>	
GCE (A/L)	18.8	Production	68.5
<u>Professional qualification</u>		Administration	6.3
No	6.3	Marketing/Merchandising	6.3
Yes	93.7	Accounting and Finance	6.3
Fully qualified	50.0	Quality assurance	6.3
Intermediate	40.6	Information technology	6.3
Basic Level	03.1		

Method of data collection

A self-administered questionnaire was developed to address the dimensions of the study. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part addressed the transfer of technology components. The questions were designed based on variables introduced by the Technology Atlas Team (1987), Sharif (1988), and the Asian and Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology (1989). The second part addressed the cultural dimensions. The questions were designed based on variables used in earlier studies (De Silva, 2003; Zerkowitz, 1998). As expatriates are not in the country to respond to the survey, we also included a separate set of questions to evaluate the extent to which locals have understood the expatriates' behaviour. For both the first and second parts of the questionnaire, a Likert scale was used. The final part of the questionnaire addressed the characteristics of the respondents, which are given in Table 2. The questionnaire

was pilot tested by giving it to five staff members who were involved in the technology transfer project. After making necessary alterations and modifications, the questionnaire was distributed to collect responses.

Methods of data analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS. To describe the extent to which technology components have been transferred and to describe the cultural dimensions, weighted mean values were used. Interpretations of mean values are given in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Level of transfer of technology components

Weighed mean	Technoware	Humanware	Orgaware	Inforware
$x \leq 1$	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
$1 < x \leq 2$	Low	Low	Low	Low
$2 < x \leq 3$	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
$3 < x \leq 4$	High	High	High	High
$4 < x \leq 5$	Very High	Very High	Very High	Very High

Table 4. Ranking of cultural dimensions

Weighed mean	Power distance	Individualism- collectivism	Masculinity- femininity	Uncertainty avoidance
$x \leq 1$	Low	Individualistic	Femininity	Low
$1 < x \leq 2$	Low	Individualistic	Femininity	Low
$2 < x \leq 3$	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
$3 < x \leq 4$	High	Collectivist	Masculinity	High
$4 < x \leq 5$	High	Collectivist	Masculinity	High

To identify the relationships among transfer of technology components and cultural dimensions, regression analysis was used. As more reliable regression analysis can be obtained by eliminating outliers, the “select cases” procedure was used.

Results

The results of the study are presented in three parts. The first part presents the findings in relation to the transfer of manufacturing process technology components. The second part presents the findings in relation to cultural dimensions. The third part presents findings on whether there is a relationship between cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing process technology components.

Analysis of the transfer of technology components

The data given in Table 5 shows high transfer of all the manufacturing process technology components. The transfer of the technoware component obtained a mean value of 3.99. The result for the transfer of the humanware component obtained a mean value of 3.59. The transfer of both orgaware and inforware components obtained equal mean values ($x=3.53$), which does not deviate much from the transfer of the humanware component.

Table 5. Transfer of manufacturing process technology components

Component	Mean	SD
Technoware	3.99	0.59
Humanware	3.59	0.79
Orgaware	3.53	0.80
Inforware	3.53	0.71

The detailed analysis of the transfer of manufacturing process technology components is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. The detailed analysis of the transfer of manufacturing technology components

Component	Subcomponent	Mean	SD
Technoware	Level of patterns, moulds, fixtures & tools	3.61	0.91
	Material handling & containers	3.78	0.87
	Usage of specialized equipments	4.00	0.71
	Infrastructure & utilities	4.28	0.58
Humanware	Contact Humanware:		
	Machine operators	3.69	0.78
	Shop floor supervisors	3.66	1.00
	Support Humanware:		
	Maintenance crew	3.63	0.90
	Planners, quality assurance & production people	3.52	1.02
	Software specialists	3.50	0.98
Orgaware	Work conventions	3.63	1.07
	Work organization	3.44	1.26
	Work facilitation	3.50	1.07
	Work evaluation	3.22	1.03
	Work modification	3.53	0.84
Inforeware	Technoware specific inforeware (TSI):		
	Technoware attribute inforeware (<i>tai</i>)	3.69	0.78
	Technoware operating inforeware (<i>toi</i>)	3.69	0.85
	Technoware maintenance inforeware (<i>tmi</i>)	3.69	0.78
	Technoware performance-enhancing inforeware (<i>tpi</i>)	3.03	1.20
	Technoware design inforeware (<i>tdi</i>)	2.80	1.15
	Humanware specific inforeware (HIS):		
	Humanware foundation inforeware (<i>hfi</i>)	3.23	0.92
	Humanware back-up inforeware (<i>hbi</i>)	3.22	0.97
	Orgaware specific inforeware (OSI):		
	Orgaware back-up inforeware (<i>obi</i>)	3.84	0.72
	Orgaware enhancing inforeware (<i>oei</i>)	3.81	0.69

According to Table 6, all technoware, humanware, orgaware, and inforeware subcomponents reveal high transfer, except *tdi* ($x=2.8$). Ramanathan (1994) states that the transferee should ensure that the *tai*, *toi*, *tmi*, and *hfi* elements of inforeware are transferred. In the study, all of these components (*tai*, *toi*, and *tmi*) reveal high transfer. Further, *tpi*, *hbi*, and OSI components of inforeware and all the components of orgaware, which are unlikely to be transferred through the purchase of plant and equipment, have also revealed high transfer. However, *tdi*, another important component of inforeware, which would also be unlikely to be transferred through the purchase of plant and equipment, obtained a mean value of 2.8, revealing moderate transfer.

Analysis of cultural dimensions

According to Table 7, power distance could be interpreted as high ($x=3.13$). The results of individualism-collectivism could be interpreted as neither individualistic nor collectivistic ($x=2.97$); so does the masculinity-femininity ($x=2.72$). The results of uncertainty avoidance can be interpreted as high ($x=3.81$).

Table 7. Analysis of cultural dimensions

Dimension	Mean	SD
Power distance	3.13	0.87
Individualism-collectivism	2.97	0.47
Masculinity-femininity	2.72	0.72
Uncertainty avoidance	3.81	0.53

A set of questions was asked to investigate the extent to which locals have understood the expatriates' behaviour. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Analysis of understanding between parties (in locals' perception)

Dimension	Mean	SD
Understating of personal behaviours of expatriates	3.15	.70
Understanding of the expatriate's culture	3.52	.53
Expatriates' understanding of the local culture	2.00	1.42
Expatriates' adjustment to local culture	3.13	.64
Level of communication between parties	3.64	.67

The data reveal that local staff members' understanding of expatriates' behaviour is good. All aspects investigated obtained mean values above average, except for local staff members' perception of expatriates' understanding of the local culture. However, this mean value should be taken into account with caution, as the standard deviation has also taken a high value.

Analysis of cultural dimensions and the transfer of technology components

Data was analyzed to find out whether there is a relationship between cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing process technology components. The results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Cultural dimensions and the transfer of technology components

Item	F.	Sig.
Power distance & transfer of technology components	.641	.638 ^a
Individualism-collectivism & transfer of technology components	2.36	.078 ^a
Masculinity-femininity & transfer of technology components	1.37	.271 ^a
Uncertainty avoidance & transfer of technology components	.936	.458 ^a

a: predictors: Inforware, Technoware, Orgaware, Humanware

The data reveal that there is no significant linear relationship between any of the cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing process technology components. Therefore, all four hypotheses could not be accepted in our study.

Conclusions and implications

The results of the investigation revealed high transfer of the components of the manufacturing process technology. The results of the cultural dimensions revealed that the respondents are high in power distance, neutral in individualism-collectivism and masculinity-femininity, and high in uncertainty avoidance. However, the investigation did not reveal any significant linear relationship between any of the cultural dimensions and the transfer of manufacturing process technology components. Therefore, though literature emphasises that cultural factors could affect cross-cultural project work, it is not evident from our investigation. This in a way supports the arguments of Akuratiyagamage (2003).

The purpose of the investigation is to understand how Hofstede's national culture dimensions could add value to manufacturing technology transfer research and what is the role these dimensions could play in future technology transfer research. Therefore, our contributions to the literature are twofold.

First, the investigation tried to use Hofstede's culture dimensions in manufacturing technology transfer research, an area that has not been touched on in the literature before. In designing the research, we wanted to broaden our understanding of how Hofstede's framework could help to develop a theoretical basis to investigate the level of manufacturing technology transfer. Based on the embodiment forms perspective of technology, we proposed a possible approach to accelerate the development of theory. The polytrophic components of manufacturing technology and Hofstede's dimensions provided us with a lens to develop hypotheses. The findings of the investigation do not eliminate the possibility of conducting further research to improve the usability of the framework and to test its validity in the context of technology transfer.

Second, our investigation gave insight into how Hofstede's dimensions could be used as independent, moderating, and control variables in future studies, to make meaningful contributions in this topic area. There is an avenue for further investigations to find out whether there are any non-linear relationships among cultural dimensions and the transfer of technology components. Though we have not found significant relationships among cultural dimensions and the transfer of technology components, the framework of the study can be reapplied in the future to investigate whether cultural aspects affect the transfer of manufacturing process technology in different organisational settings. In stating this, we are not ignoring the fact that the components of technology transferred will depend on the background and nature of the activities of the firms involved in the transfer process. However, it should be noted that researchers have recently questioned the over-reliance on Hofstede's national culture dimensions (Ford et al 2003) in investigating group or individual level. It should be noted that it is not our contention that Hofstede's national culture dimensions are the sole appropriate approach to investigate issues relating to technology transfer at the organisational level. Therefore, there is a need for a more theoretical approach to studying culture at an individual/organizational level, which could provide a complementary research perspective, not necessarily a competing one.

Finally, the framework of the study provided us with a "handle" on the difficult concept of culture and technology transfer, and allowed us to conduct a quantitative investigation. However, it would be unwise to assume any aspect of reality is quantifiable by a single measure. Therefore, future research based on the technology transfer and culture should rely on multiple methodologies and epistemologies in furthering the understanding.

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